

The digital revolution in landscape planning – A scoping literature review

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Abstract

Landscape planning is a multi-phase, iterative process that involves research, synthesis, ideation, and implementation. Digital technologies provide new tools and methods to make the process more efficient, effective, and innovative. They have revolutionized data acquisition, processing, and presentation speed and accuracy. Geographical information systems (GIS), remote sensing (RS), and digital modeling are integral parts of everyday landscape planning practice. Digital technologies have become indispensable, reshaping how designers, planners, and policymakers approach the intricate task of creating sustainable and resilient environments. The digital revolution we are witnessing encompasses a broader set of tools, devices, and resources that have not yet been fully incorporated into the landscape planning process. Through a scoping review of 53,114 papers from the last decade, this research explores the variety of digital technologies supporting landscape planning. It uncovers emerging trends and discovers the state-of-the-art digitalization of landscape planning.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Rationale

We live in the digital revolution era. Digital technologies are changing how we live, work, and communicate. Landscape and urban planners can benefit from a vast range of rapidly developing digital technologies such as big data, programming tools, and software applications to gather, analyze, synthesize, and visualize data. Among the most widely used technologies is Geographic Information Systems (GIS), which, together with associated technologies such as Global Positioning System (GPS) and digital image processing, provides a spatial framework for analyzing and visualizing diverse layers of data and supports professionals in making informed decisions by integrating information about land use, vegetation, topography, and infrastructure (Hendrix et al., 1988; Kempa & Lovett, 2019). Current GIS systems, including WebGIS, offer capabilities to assist the whole planning process (Pietsch, 2012) and support it with complex natural system modeling, analysis, and ideation (Kempa & Lovett, 2019). Remote sensing, such as satellite imagery and aerial surveys, complement GIS by offering real-time data on landscape dynamics, enabling planners to monitor changes and identify potential areas of concern (Bhartiya et al., 2022). Building Information Modeling (BIM) has gained prominence for its ability to create 3D models that integrate physical and functional aspects of landscapes, share data and information, and optimize communication throughout the process (Gnädinger & Roth, 2021). It facilitates collaborative planning and enables stakeholders to visualize and understand the impact of design decisions on the environment and community (Brückner & Remy, 2021).

We combined digital technology (DT) and landscape planning (LP) concepts to map emerging trends in the last decade.

The general definition of digital technology encompasses a wide range of technologies, tools, services, and applications that use different hardware and software to facilitate information creation, storage, processing, transmission, and display. The key characteristics of DT include binary representation, digital processing, and storage of the data, facilitation of transmission of the information over digital communication networks, reproducibility, precision, and interactivity and engagement of users with digital content manipulation (Ciarli et al., 2021; Ciriello et al., 2018; Tulinayo et al., 2018).

Landscape planning (LP) is defined as a practice focused on the sustainable use of natural and cultural resources while reconciling competing land use priorities presents complex interdisciplinary challenges (Ahern, 1995; Fabos, 1979; Steiner, 2000; Steiner, 2017; Zube, 1986). It applies to all landscape contexts, such as urban, rural, natural, etc. The contemporary landscape planning concept originated in the 1920s as a response to the expansion of cities and the degradation of land resources. One of the pioneers was Benton MacKaye, who advocated for environmentally responsive land use planning. He highlighted the danger of “metropolitan invasion,” an urban sprawl based on a decision-making process based only on economic, political, and social factors. He recognized the interaction between man and the environment as vital to development. He called for action to preserve natural landscape features to avoid natural hazards and destructive environmental effects such as floods (MacKaye, 1928).

With the growing amount of data about complex landscape systems, intelligent tools, such as remote sensing, computerized data storage, retrieval, and manipulation systems for analysis

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and modeling, were needed to support landscape planning processes (Fabos, 1979). It became impossible to reach the full potential of planning based on environmental landscape principles without utilizing emerging technologies to gather, manipulate, analyze, and synthesize the data.

To address challenges related to the analysis and synthesis of complex natural systems, landscape planners and landscape architects have actively engaged in the development of geographical information systems (GIS) as comprehensive frameworks for their work. One of the early pioneers in this field was Ian McHarg, who introduced the overlay site analysis methodology, which used transparent map layers to evaluate the landscape (McHarg, 1969). His layer cake landscape planning method laid the theoretical foundation for constructing GIS databases. McHarg witnessed the establishment of GIS at Harvard School of Design in the 1960s. In the early 1990s, he collaborated on a prototype database for a national ecological inventory in the United States, which was submitted to the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) in 1993 (Steiner, 2017). In the meantime, the computer revolution of the 70s and the creation of microcomputers advanced opportunities to include GIS technologies in the planning routine. In parallel, the spatial data, spurred on by the existence of a technology to support it, created the demand for appropriate information systems (Harris & Batty, 1993). In the late 80s, Planning Support Systems (PSS), computer-based tools to support planners in planning-specific activities, were developed. Based on GIS, modeling systems, and user-friendly graphical interfaces, PSSs enabled planners to explore “what if?” scenarios (Geertman et al., 2020).

The combination of information technology and the Internet in the 90s led to the development of the technology-based Internet society (Susskind & Susskind, 2015). The Internet has enabled access to large quantities of content and facilitated the creation of online collaboration. At the same time, the need for an interdisciplinary and multi-stakeholder process led to the introduction of the geodesign framework by Steinitz (2012). Geodesign is an approach to knowledge-based planning and design and involves complex processes through which multidisciplinary teams collaborate in cocreating sustainable change scenarios. It integrates Geographic Information Science methods and tools to transform spatial data into relevant knowledge for informed, collaborative, and negotiated design and decision-making (Campagna, 2016). The development of geodesign framework and increasing digital capabilities in computer processing power, digital storage, and internet speeds during the last decade marked exponential growth in literature and research on the topic.

Gordon Moore, the author of the famous Moore’s Law in 1965, already predicted an accelerated pace of information technology due to miniaturization in the semiconductor industry (Moore, 1995). As the technology processing capability advances, the process speeds up even more each year. Digital innovations will continue to shape all fields, including landscape planning. According to the ranking of mega-trends developed by Moffitt (2018), the five most emerging technologies for the next decade are Artificial intelligence (AI), which processes vast amounts of data; the Internet of Things (IoT), including sensors and Information and Communication Technology (ICT); Mobile and Social Internet, including Social Networks/Media; Blockchain and Big Data, including predictive analytics. Other technologies such as Automation, Robots (Drones and UAVs), Immersive Media, Mobile Technologies, Cloud Computing, 3D Printing, Voice Assistants, Collaborative Technologies, Geospatial Technologies, and Smart Cities present high significance for the LP process. In the annual McKinsey Global Survey (McKinsey, 2023) on the current state of AI, explosive growth of

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generative AI (genAI) tools is highlighted. The AI's public availability allows for experimentation with the tools, and respondents expect the new capabilities to transform their industries.

Recently, several publications have focused on technology in landscape planning (Cantrell & Holzman, 2016; Geertman et al., 2020; Sabri & Witte, 2023). They discuss the advancement of DT in LP-related tasks by presenting case studies, innovative applications, and best practices. Daniel and Pettit (2021) suggest that despite the plethora of new digital tools, software, devices, and planning initiatives, little up-to-date scholarly research has been published exploring the advancement of systematic changes and impacts on planning practice. Our research aims to fill this gap by systematically mapping emerging trends to inform planners, policymakers, and researchers about digital technologies in landscape planning.

1.2. Objectives

Through the scoping review of 53,114 papers, we aim to systematically map the research done at the intersection of landscape planning and digital technologies. By comprehensive analysis, we identify trends and emerging technological approaches to planning. We formulated the following research questions:

Q1 Which digital technologies are used in landscape planning?

Q2 What are the emerging trends, and how have they changed over the last ten years?

Q3 What are the dominant correlations between different digital technologies?

Q4 Where are the gaps for further research?

2. Materials and methods

2.1. General framework

We conducted a scoping review to synthesize the evidence and assess the scope of the literature, identifying the main concepts, theories, sources, and knowledge gaps (Tricco et al., 2018). This framework allows for preliminary systematic mapping of critical concepts and examining the extent and nature of available literature. Although it was initially developed for health sciences and medicine-related research, it has already been adopted in papers related to DT and LP (Casali et al., 2022; Hofland et al., 2018; Smith et al., 2022).

We adapted the stages proposed by Arksey and O'Malley (2005) together with the PRISMA-ScR (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses Extension for Scoping Reviews) checklist to ensure that all stages include the information required by PRISMA protocol and to improve the reporting quality and transparency during each stage of the process (PRISMA, 2018; Tricco et al., 2018). Given the data set's volume, we combined manual and automated data identification and charting (Figure 1). After formulating research questions (Section 1.2), we identified relevant literature (Section 2.2) and selected studies to analyze (Section 2.3). Then, we performed automated data charting (Section 2.4). The results (Section 3) encompass final evidence extraction and selection of sources of evidence (Section 3.1), a review of systematic literature reviews extracted from our final dataset (Section 3.2),

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bibliometric characteristics of the data set and clusters and networks analysis (Section 3.3), and identification of trends in landscape planning regarding technologies ranking and correlations between technologies (Section 3.4).

Figure 1. General framework

2.2 Sources of evidence identification

The set of keywords used for the search was based on the two concepts – landscape planning (Concept 1) and digital technology (Concept 2). The full list of keywords can be found in Appendix A - Search Strategies.

We used Scopus, Web of Science Core Collection, and Academic Search Ultimate (EBSCO platform) since they are the most extensive and relevant abstract and citation bibliographic databases (Clarivate, 2023; EBSCO, 2023; Elsevier, 2023). All papers were collected in the EndNote (2013) software, where the duplicates and retracted documents were removed.

Three searches were performed: first, to create a preliminary set, analyze it manually, identify technology-related keywords, and train ALGORITHM 1 and 2; second, to additionally train ALGORITHM 1; and third, to update the data set and apply both algorithms to perform automatic data charting.

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The eligibility criteria were as follows: peer-reviewed journal articles, conference papers, conference proceedings, book sections, and books were included in the search, and only documents published since 2012 in English were considered. Identification of the relevant papers from the set was based on the existence of both concepts in the title, abstract, or keywords.

We also applied exclusion criteria as follows (Table 1):

Table 1 Applied Exclusion Criteria

No	Criteria	Reason
1	Only one keyword concept	Papers that contained only landscape or only technology were rejected.
2	Education and design	We did not focus on educational or design applications; however, in our work, education and design were among the keywords in this paper. In the case of “landscape education (OR teaching),” sometimes it might refer to teaching communities or educating stakeholders. In the case of “design” in some publications, it was used alternatively to “planning” and vice versa. We decided to include them in the first phase and further analyze them in the second phase to ensure all relevant papers are included in the final set.
3	Management and smart city	We decided to exclude all papers related to the management and operational application of the technology, especially in transport networks or smart applications for managing, controlling, or administrating infrastructure.
4	Statistics	All papers related to purely statistical data gathering or analysis were rejected.

Finally, we identified systematic or scoping reviews using the keyword “review”, charted them manually, and included relevant items in the review of reviews (3.1).

2.3 Selecting studies

Manual data charting, identification, and grouping of technologies

The initial search was performed on February 4, 2022. We identified 39,886 items in the three databases, and after removing duplicates, 27,722 items remained in the set. At this stage, we manually analyzed 5% of the papers (1,363). Two reviewers jointly developed a data-charting form in Microsoft Access based on the literature review. We independently charted the data, identified technologies based on the authors’ declarations, discussed imprecise cases, and continuously updated the data-charting form in an iterative process.

Cohen’s kappa statistical coefficient agreement was calculated to assess the data classification’s degree of accuracy and reliability (Cohen, 1960). We used Cohen’s kappa online calculator (Scarpellini, 2022). The result was almost perfect alignment (91.77%) Cohen’s kappa 0.84. Additional 23 papers were excluded because of detected duplicates or lack of data (i.e., lack of abstracts). Finally, 684 papers were accepted, and 679 were rejected.

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The technologies were identified based on the literature and authors' declarations. We determined groups and subgroups by the types of technologies (Table 2). We manually checked all discrepancies between both reviewers and produced the final aligned set. Since our analysis included only title, abstract, and keywords, it was impossible to determine subgroups in all technology groups. Many authors were not specific in the technology they used and in the keywords they mentioned, for example, RS, instead of more specific imaging radar.

The CAD group included Computer Assisted Drafting and 3d Printing; GIS encompassed systems, software, and GIS-based algorithms; RS contained all types of sensors; Robotic included Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAV), Urban Air Mobility (UAM), drones, and other robots; Social Media included Social networks, Social news, Blogging, Bookmarking, Media sharing, and others. The Other Digital Modelling included mathematical and statistical modelling, not indicated by authors as decision/planning support systems and AI-related technologies. It was mainly related to phenomena and modelling of relationships between phenomena such as, land use changes, and hydrological, climatic, or ecological corridors models.

Table 2. Groups and subgroups by the types of technologies

Group	Subgroups
3D MODELLING	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Building Information Modelling (BIM) • Land/Landscape Information Modeling (LIM) • Point Cloud • Rendering • 3D Scanning • 3D Models
AI-RELATED	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Artificial Intelligence (AI) • Deep Learning (DL) • Machine Learning (ML) • Multiagent Systems (MAS) • Other AI
CAD (Computer-Aided Design)	No subgroups
DATA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Science • Data Mining • Big Data • Crowdsourcing • Open Data • Other Data
DECISION SUPORT SYSTEMS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decision/Planning Support Systems (DSS/PSS) • Multicriteria Decision Analysis (MCDA)
GIS	No subgroups
OTHER DIGITAL MODELING	No subgroups
OTHER ICT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Global Positioning System (GPS) • Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) • Information and Communication Technology (ICT) • Blockchain • Cloud computing, • Internet of Things (IoT) • Devices
REMOTE SENSING	No subgroups
ROBOTIC	No subgroups
SOCIAL MEDIA	No subgroups
VR/AR/MR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Virtual Reality (VR) • Augmented Reality (AR)

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• Mixed Reality (MR)

ALGORITHM 1 (BERT) was trained and tested based on our decisions to accept or reject the source. The list of technologies with their groups and respective keywords was integrated into ALGORITHM 2 and ALGORITHM 3.

The final source codes we adapted and developed are available on GitHub (DRLP, 2024).

ALGORITHM 1 (BERT) adapting and training

After assessing the final set, we noticed that some technologies were revealed in just a few papers while others were used more broadly. Therefore, we had to find the best way to classify larger datasets, including a balanced dataset of acceptance results and an unbalanced dataset for technology classification. A set of Python scripts was implemented, and several classification algorithms were tested for that purpose.

Two programming environments were used for testing:

1) Online Google Colaboratory (GC), with Python 3.10, pytorch, and transformers for algorithms that require more computing power and execute code on Google's cloud servers. GC is a product from Google Research that allows one to write and execute arbitrary code through the browser and is exceptionally well suited to machine learning, data analysis, and education (GoogleColab, 2023).

2) Local personal computer (PC) with Spyder IDE (2023), a free and open source scientific environment written in Python, with Anaconda® Distribution Python 3.8 64-bit and nltk, pandas, sklearn, xgboost libraries.

In GC, the BERT (Bidirectional Encoder Representation from Transformers) model (Devlin et al., 2018), extracted from kaggle (JSeb, 2000), with its subvariants (bert-base-uncased, scibert_scivocab_uncased, SR_bert-base-uncased) were tested, while in local PC Logistic Regression, Naive Bayes, XGBoost algorithms with tf-idf and w2v models were tested. The research matrix covered different algorithms and preprocessing techniques like consistency checks, removing records with empty values, stopword removal, tokenization, and lemmatization. We applied several settings depending on the algorithm: penalty, learning rate, gamma, train/test split rate, number of epochs, dataset balancing, shuffling, and some others of minor significance. We tested the combination of input parameters: Abstracts only, Keywords only, Titles only, Notes only, Abstracts+Titles+Keywords, Abstracts+Titles+Keywords+Notes.

We received the following results for machine learning algorithms tested on PC: accuracy of up to 80% for single parameter dataset, i.e., abstracts, keywords, titles or notes only; accuracy of up to 84% for Logistic Regression tf-idf model and up to 81% for Naive Bayes, Logistic Regression w2v model and XGB classifier with combination Abstracts+Titles+Keyword.

Deep Learning algorithm BERT resulted in up to 86 % overall accuracy.

We validated trained algorithms with a new set of articles generated on January 3, 2023. The same search was conducted in the three databases, results were exported to EndNote20, and duplicates were removed when checked against the initial EndNote library, resulting in the identification of 3,568 new documents. The initial best results for accuracy were 80% for Logistic regression and 82% for BERT. Misclassified records were reviewed to compare with algorithm results and then agreed upon among researchers. We repeated validation and received 85% for Logistic Regression, 84% for Naive Bayes, and 85% for BERT.

The joined dataset consisted of the initial database, and January 3rd databases were retrained with an accuracy of 86% with the BERT (base) model made from Abstracts, Titles, and Keywords.

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We applied parameters for the model (Table 3) for acceptance/rejection prediction on the May 10 Dataset (53,114 records).

Table 3. The best training results obtained during the test, implemented in the study

Overall Results					
F1 Score (Weighted):	0.86				
Accuracy	0.86				
Per class results					
Class	Precision	Recall	F1	Support	Accuracy
0	0.86	0.86	0.86	151	130/151 (0.86)
1	0.86	0.85	0.86	151	129/151 (0.86)
Confusion Matrix					
Class	0	1			
0	130	21			
1	22	129			

BERT gave the most stable, good results for different datasets and parameters. Although Wang et al. (2022) proposed a model with better than BERT results in the literature classification, our primary goal was to do a cross-technology literature review in the landscape planning area, rather than building a state-of-the-art model for literature review and so well-known, broadly verified classification technics were used.

2.4 Data charting

ALGORITHM 2 (Keyword based) for technology detection

The technology keywords were not evenly distributed and did not fit well in the machine-learning algorithms we tested. Although there are machine learning algorithms for unbalanced datasets, due to too many parameters, we decided to develop keyword-based technology detection. Therefore, we developed ALGORITHM 2 using a set of keywords to perform automated data charting and identify groups and subgroups of technologies. Keywords for technology detection were added in adding/checking cycles up to receiving expected results. The main criteria were eliminating false negative records while false positive were monitored and noted but less critical for final analysis. After reaching Cohen's kappa 0.81, we used ALGORITHM 2 for an automated data extraction.

VOSViewer for text mining and ALGORITHM 3 for automated data charting

We performed cluster and network analysis using VOSViewer (CWTS, 2024) to perform text mining and visualize co-occurrence networks of important terms and applications extracted from titles and abstracts.

Finally, we analyzed the dataset of the studies using ALGORITHM 3 (a set of statistical tools in Python). We researched and summarized the total number of mentions appearing yearly and performed correlation analyses inside and between groups and subgroups of technologies. We used a correlation matrix with the Pearson coefficient.

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3. Results

3.1 Final evidence extraction and selection of sources of evidence

The final search and evidence extraction was performed on May 10, 2023. We identified 53,114 items in the three databases, and after removing duplicates and retracted papers, 35,972 items remained in the set. We applied ALGORITHM 1 to identify relevant sources.

Figure 2. PRISMA flow diagram

After applying ALGORITHM 2 (Keywords-based), we noticed that 239 sources were accepted by ALGORITHM 1 (BERT), but no technology was identified by ALGORITHM 2 (false positive records). We screened these items manually to ensure we did not miss any novel, previously unidentified technology. Since that was not the case, they were removed from the set.

As a result of our procedure, we obtained 15,443 records, classified into twelve groups of technologies based on authors' declarations.

3.2. Review of existing reviews extracted from the dataset

210 papers were identified as literature reviews. The full texts were analyzed manually, following the same acceptance/rejection criteria based on the existence of both concepts. 56 papers were declared by authors as scoping or systematic reviews.

We identified two main types of reviews:

1. Technologies for landscape planning. It is the most relevant group dedicated to applications of technologies for landscape planning. It includes cognitive systems and frameworks for planning (Giler-Velásquez et al., 2021; Recalde et al., 2020), insights for using crowdsource platforms and social media (Chaves et al., 2019), participation and interaction during the process (De Siqueira et al., 2022) use of GIS, remote sensing

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(Ouchra et al., 2022) and semantic web technologies (von Richthofen et al., 2022) for urban planning.

2. Technologies related to landscape planning (for the complete list of papers, see Appendix B). In this group, the papers do not focus on landscape planning, but they recognize the potential applications of technologies in LP. We identified three subtypes:
 - a. Technology-focused papers. The topics were exploring the use of the technologies for specific tasks, analysis, or information processing that might be useful but not limited to the planning process, such as geocoding, location-based networks, GIS applications, RS used for object and risk management, artificial intelligence applications, use of UAVs, mix realities, digital twins and social media. This category also includes support systems and decision-making tools such as multiobjective optimization, MultiCriteria Decision Analysis (MCDA), and decision support tools and systems.
 - b. Papers that are on the intersection of technology and other topics that eventually can be related to the landscape planning process but not focusing on LP, such as GPS and ecological monitoring, RS supporting ecological value assessment, green infrastructure and technologies, computer simulations, and land value, health and mobile technologies, GIS used in a variety of context or more broadly technology and spatial changes.
 - c. Smart city concept. This group focused on governance and management - operational applications of technology in smart cities rather than landscape planning. The focus was on the management and governance, technological development of smart city, semantic technology, relationships with industry 4.0, integration of blockchain technology, data-driven sustainable cities, and smart city systems security.

Figure 3. The focus of the literature reviews

All papers (56) included both concepts (landscape and technology), but 50 did not explore the intersection between technology and landscape planning; however, they acknowledged their applications in LP. 25 papers were technology-focused, discussing the application or development of a particular technology; 15 focused on the smart city concept and were related to technologies, smart governance, and management; and 10 papers reviewed research on the intersection of technology and other topics. Technology dedicated to landscape planning was identified in 6 papers; in five of them, only the intersection between specific technology and landscape planning was discussed without a broader overview of the digital landscape. In one article (von Richthofen et al., 2022), the authors focused on Semantic Web Technologies, an

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innovation area in the digital revolution. They suggested considering a shift in the approach to the LP process to address the rise of DT. They proposed four meta-practices (MP): representational MP, evaluative MP, projective MP, and synthetic MP. The data-synthetic meta-practice defined as the act of managing, gathering, using, creating, and synthesizing data, information, and knowledge, supported by Semantic Web Technologies, would become a core of collaboration between LP: planners, policymakers and scholars, and IT: data scientist, programmers, and software developers.

3.3. Bibliometric characteristics and networks of extracted database

We gathered 11,447 journal articles, 3,352 conference proceedings, 377 conference papers, 235 book sections, 28 books, three cases, and one generic. The extracted dataset included numerous papers from authors affiliated with more than 8,000 institutions worldwide. They were published by 876 publishers in more than 4,300 journals. Predominantly represented publishers are Elsevier Ltd/B.V, MDPI, Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers Inc., Springer, Taylor and Francis Ltd, International Society for Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing, Institute of Physics Publishing (from 2,585 publications by Elsevier group to 260 by Institute of Physics Publishing). The ten most popular journals are Sustainability (441), Remote Sensing (Basel) (312), The International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences (269), and IOP conference series, Earth and Environmental Science (264), Landscape and Urban Planning (213), Science of the Total Environment (212), Sustainable Cities and Society (187), International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health (168), ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information (158) Building and Environment (147).

We performed clusters and network analysis using VOSViewer (Figure 4). As a result of the text mining (abstracts and titles), six main thematic clusters could be identified: 1) land, including land use/land cover, land surface temperature (LST), and forests; 2) climatic conditions modeling; 3) water management and hydrological performance modeling; 4) user-oriented planning process, perception, and walkability; 5) RS, mapping, and 3D modeling technologies including accuracy, extraction, segmentation etc; 6) other, miscellaneous content related to copyrights, property, and different publishers.

The most prominent concept, “accuracy” (1,729 occurrences), is related to the precision of technology in different fields and applications and is linked to 3,734 other keywords across all six clusters. The second one, “user” (1,264 occurrences/3,295 links), is strongly linked to clusters 4 and 5, with a minor connection to clusters 1 (“land cover” only), 3, and 6. It has no links to cluster 2 (climate). Finally, the “planning process” (416 occurrences/1,585 links) is linked within its own cluster (4) only. It is related to “user,” “web,” “citizen,” and “participation”.

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Figure 5 Total number of papers per indicated group of technology

Figure 6. Number of papers in groups of technologies per year

Since some groups included the subgroups of technologies, we identified the number of papers in the subgroups.

In the AI-related group (4,124 papers), the most significant was ML (2,998), which appeared in 73% of papers, followed by DL, Other AI, AI, and MAS (Figure 7). The number of papers in this group grew significantly over the last decade (134 papers in 2012 to 824 papers in 2022). A significant rise in the number of publications can be observed in 2019.

In Other ICT (2,335 papers), seven subgroups were identified (Figure 8). Devices appeared in 56% of papers, IoT almost 25%, and GPS 20%, followed by GPS, ICT, Cloud, and GNSS. The least significant concept is Blockchain, which appeared in only five papers. The rise in the number of papers in the ICT group is relatively stable, with minimal variations (from 70 in 2012 to 197 in 2022). A significant increase can be observed in IoT (9 in 2013 to 102 in 2022).

Figure 7. Number of papers in subgroups of AI-Related group of technology per year

Figure 8. Number of papers in subgroups of Other ICT group of technology per year

3D Modelling (2,320 papers) has grown slowly over the last decade (Figure 9). It includes six subgroups. The most prominent, the 3D Models group, was represented in 70% of all

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documents in this category, followed by 3D Scanning (28%), Point Cloud, BIM, Rendering, and LIM (only nine papers starting in 2016).

The number of papers in the Data group (2,268 papers) significantly rose from 52 in 2012 to 400 in 2022 (Figure 10). The most relevant of the six groups (in terms of both the total number of papers and the most dynamic growth over the decade) was Open Data (appeared in 36% of papers), followed by Crowdsourcing (26%), Big Data (25%), Data Mining, Other Data, and Data Science (starting in 2015).

Figure 9. Number of papers in subgroups of 3D Modelling group of technology per year

Figure 10. Number of papers in subgroups of Data group of technology per year

Decision Support System encompasses key technologies in landscape and urban planning (Figure 11). This group was indicated by authors in 1,426 papers. We divided it into two subgroups: MCDA/AHP subgroup (65%, 926 mentions, and PSS/DSS (35%, 595 mentions). We also observed a constant increase in the number of papers in MCDA/AHP subgroup, while the number of new papers per year in the PSS/DSS group was relatively constant.

The VR/AR/MR group (3 subgroups) appeared in 507 papers (Figure 12). The most significant was VR (370/73%), followed by AR, and MR. The group and subgroups have shown stable, gradual growth since 2017.

Figure 11. Number of papers in subgroups of Decision Support Systems group of technology per year

Figure 12. Number of papers in subgroups of VR/AR/MR group of technology per year

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Finally, we ranked identified technologies according to the number of papers that mentioned them (Box 1).

Box 1. Ranking of identified technologies (number of papers/percent of the total number of sources of evidence in the final dataset)

1. Remote Sensing (9481/61.39%)	12. Other AI (699/4.53%),	24. Data Mining (245/1.59%)
2. GIS (6117/39.61%)	13. 3D Scanning (650/4.21%)	25. ICT (241/1.56%),
3. Other Digital Modelling (4505/29.17)	14. Robotic (599/3.88%)	26. CAD (183/1.19%)
4. ML (2998/19.41%)	15. PSS/DSS (595/3.85%)	27. Cloud (167/1.08%),
5. 3D Models (1625/10.52%)	16. IoT (581/3.76%)	28. AR (159/1.03%)
6. Devices (1311/8.49%)	17. AI 502 (3.25%)	29. GNSS (151/0.98%)
7. DL (1185/7.67%)	18. MAS (501/3.24%)	30. Other Data (137/0.89%)
8. Open Data (1182/7.65%)	19. GPS (472/3.06%)	31. Rendering (91/0.59%)
9. MCDA/AHP 926/6%	20. Social Media (379/2.45%)	32. Data Science (54/0.35%)
10. Crowdsourcing (836/5.41%)	21. VR (370/2.40%)	33. MR (32/0.21%)
11. Big Data (808/5.23%)	22. Point Cloud (344/2.23%),	34. LIM (9/0.06%)
	23. BIM (331/2.14%)	35. Blockchain (5/0.03%)

The numbers percentages show the share of technology in all analyzed articles. They overlap; therefore, we performed a correlation analysis to illustrate their relationships.

3.4 Correlations between technologies

The analysis of correlations within and between groups of technologies revealed predominantly small correlations. This paper presents results where the obtained coefficient exceeds ($p \geq 0.1$). We also decided to present only positive correlations because they directly respond to our research questions. Moreover, the negative correlations mainly result from our grouping procedure or lack of authors' declarations, which we consider a study limitation explained in the conclusions.

We found the strongest correlations inside the following groups of technologies (Figure 13):

- 1) Data: Big Data with Open Data (0.41) and Crowdsourcing (0.48); Crowdsourcing with Open Data (0.39);
- 2) 3D Modelling: Point Cloud with 3D Models (0.22) and 3D Scanning (0.42); 3D Models with 3D Scanning (0.24) and Rendering (0.11);
- 3) AI-Related: AI with DL(0.11) and ML(0,37); DL with ML (0.59);
- 4) Other ICT: GPS with GNSS (0.44) and Devices (0.16); IoT with ICT(0.13);
- 5) VR/MR/AR: VR with MR (0.1) and AR (0.14); AR with MR (0.16).

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Figure 13. Correlations graph inside groups of technologies

The correlation matrix between the main groups of technologies (Appendix C) identified ten key pairs of correlated technologies from the last decade of literature (Figure 14, marked in bold in Table 4). Notably, the strongest correlations occurred in the technologies related to the Data group, as it reached four correlation pairs. The frequent appearance of Data alongside RS revealed robust connections between Big Data (0.18), Crowdsourcing (0.11), Open Data (0.14), and Data Mining (0.1). The second significant correlation was observed between Data and Social Media, with notable connections between Big Data (0.11) and Crowdsourcing (0.15). A growing trend in literature since 2016 has been identified for correlations between Data and AI-Related technologies, notably Data Mining with Machine Learning (0.12). Additionally, Data correlated with the Other ICT group, where the connection of Big Data with IoT was evident (0.11).

Besides Data resulting in four constant correlation pairs, we found that two groups of technologies (RS and 3d Modelling) have three constant correlation pairs each. While VR/AR/MR and AI-Related noted two correlation pairs, six groups (Other ICT, Robotic, CAD, Social Media, GIS and DSS) reached only one constant correlation pair (Figure 14).

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Decision support systems – GIS	0.13	x	0.15	0.16	0.12	x	0.11	0.15	0.11	0.16	0.13	0.14	0.19	848
Other ICT – Robotic	x	0.1	x	x	0.14	0.15	0.13	0.12	0.12	0.1	0.11	0.14	x	190
Other ICT – VR/AR/MR	x	0.14	x	x	0.1	x	0.14	x	x	0.12	0.1	0.1	x	161
Other ICT – Social Media	x	x	0.12	x	0.13	x	0.1	0.12	x	0.1	x	x	x	112
Other ICT – Remote Sensing	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	0.12	0.1	x	x	0.12	0.11	1666
Remote sensing – Social Media	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	0.12	x	0.11	x	x	x	298

The third significant group, RS, exhibited correlations with Data (0.21) AI-Related (0.13), and 3D Modeling (0.11) groups.

Moreover, VR/AR/MR group expressed correlations with 3D Modelling (0.12) and CAD (0.11). Correlation with CAD started in 2016.

Then, AI-Related technologies showed correlations with RS, with ML (0.14) being the most notable. Several fragmented connections of AI-Related group were observed, including a decreasing trend with DDS and Robotics. The correlation with Other ICT emerged in 2023, while the correlation with Social Media appeared in 2018.

A rising trend in a correlation between DDS and GIS was noted (0.13), particularly with MCDA (0.13). Similarly, a growing trend was observed for the Other ICT group, which began correlating with Robotics (increasing visibly), VR/AR/MR, and Social Media (both fragmented). Moreover, the connection between RS and Social Media emerged in 2018 and continued in 2020.

4. Summary and discussion

Summary

We performed an automated data selection and charting based on 53,114 records identified from three of the most relevant literature databases. As a result, our research analyzed 15,443 papers retrieved on May 10, 2023. There is a dynamically growing body of literature on the subject, but the sources are scattered worldwide and in many journals. They are generally published in three main groups of journals: 1) computer science or particular technology-specific, 2) earth and environmental science, and 3) planning-related. Journals addressing planning are in the minority.

A review of reviews indicated that only 11% of papers (6) were planning process-oriented. Among six thematic clusters, the planning process was primarily connected to citizen participation and walkability, with weak connections to other clusters. Technology was mainly used for research related to RS and modelling of land use changes, climatic conditions, and hydrological performance.

We found 35 technologies and grouped them into 12 groups. Our study revealed five leading technologies: 1) Remote Sensing, 2) GIS, 3) Other Digital Modeling, 4) AI-Related (specifically Machine Learning), and 5) 3D Modelling. For all technologies, the number of papers presented an increasing trend. However, they vary in terms of dynamics.

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Mentions of technologies in papers overlap, which means they are coupled. We found strong correlations inside five groups (Data, 3D Modelling, AI-Related, Other ICT, VR/AR/MR) and ten small correlations between groups.

We identified the leading reciprocal correlation between RS – Data – AI-Related (ML). Data got the highest number of constant correlation pairs (4), then RS and 3D Modelling (3), AI-Related and VR/AR/MR (2). There was no correlation between RS and GIS and DSS. 3D Modelling is correlated with VR/AR/MR, Robotic, and RS. GIS is correlated with the DSS (particularly with MCDA). The most significant correlations between subgroups from the different groups are ML and RS; VR and 3D Models and Rendering; MCDA and GIS.

Our study shows decreasing and increasing trends in correlations. The increasing trends in correlations between technologies concentrate on RS – Data – AI-Related (ML), GIS and MCDA, and 3D Modelling with VR. Several correlations emerged for the Other ICT group. The decreasing trends in correlations were detected for DSS and AI-Related group and Data with GIS.

Discussion

According to Geertman et al. (2020), there is a strong consensus across the literature on megatrends and the importance of digital technologies in supporting planning systems. On the other hand, some authors recognized the scarcity of studies on the subject and the need for a larger body of research (Daniel & Pettit, 2021; De Siqueira et al., 2022).

We identified that beyond the five leading technologies: RS, GIS, Other Digital Modeling, AI-Related, and 3D Modelling, there is a complex system of 30 other technologies related to landscape planning (LP) processes. They are not detached technologies. Ciriello et al. (2018) highlighted the convergence and generativity of DT as the main components of digital innovation. DTs are inherently dynamic; they overlap, connect, fusion, and combine previously separated components.

Depending on the scope of the research, other technologies might appear as leading ones. For example, Recalde et al. (2020), in their literature review, concluded that big data processing, analysis, and visualization are the most relevant topics. Although Big Data is not among the five leading technologies in our research (it appears in the eleventh position in the ranking), Data has strong correlations, such as the solid reciprocal correlation between RS – Data (including Big Data) – AI-Related (ML), Social Media, and Other ICT.

Sabri and Witte (2023) stated that technologies should create a collaborative and integrative ecosystem to facilitate equity, environmental sustainability, and efficiency in LP, while De Siqueira et al. (2022) highlighted the growing trend of public participation and interaction during the process, which calls for insights from crowdsourcing platforms and social media. We observed correlations between Data and Social Media, and RS and Social Media (that emerged in 2018), and the strong correlation between RS and Data, so we can confirm that the trend of enhancing citizen perspective using DT in LP is ongoing. Additionally, according to our VOSviewer analysis, the planning process is strongly related to citizen participation within its cluster.

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While Chaves et al. (2019) stressed the need for heuristics algorithms to synthesize and generate results from the crowd data input and for AI-Related technologies to deal with the diversity of data sources and the accessibility to large amounts of open data, Moffitt (2018) predicted that we would experience exponential growth in AI-Related systems. Our research supports both statements. We revealed the Data – AI-Related correlation as one of the most prominent and dynamic growth over the last decade (614%) of the AI-Related technologies group. AI might be considered a prospective game changer; however, it should be noted that the most significant contribution so far is in ML and DL, not in AI as such. This trend is very dynamic, and with the recent introduction of genAI, AI-Related algorithms might soon become standard tools in professional practice, as suggested by McKinsey report (2023).

Several correlation overlaps between technologies discussed by different authors were not confirmed in our correlation analysis. Ouchra et al. (2022) highlighted the importance of using satellite data analysis (RS) in conjunction with GIS applications, while our study did not identify RS – GIS correlation. The common denominator for RS and GIS is Data (strong correlation with RS and decreasing with GIS). On the other hand, the slow rise in the number of papers that use GIS as a keyword might suggest that it already become a standard tool for LP, and authors did not highlight the fact that they used GIS-related software in the research unless the papers address specific GIS development. A decreasing trend between GIS and Data was observed until the correlation disappeared in 2015. It might be related to the fact that we witnessed the standardization of data processing within GIS systems.

Some correlations were not captured because they are very recent or still in the experimental phase. An example might be GIS and BIM integration discussed by Gnädinger and Roth (2021).

We found the correlation between GIS and MCDA (Decision Support group), which can be considered a core of the planning process. Pietsch (2012) stressed that existing GIS systems offer the capabilities to address all phases of the LP and can support process-oriented planning introduced by Steinitz (2012), strengthening its collaborative dimension simultaneously.

Kempa and Lovett (2019) emphasized the importance of using an automated sequence of tools, such as models and scripts, during GIS analysis and evaluation. Still, surprisingly, in our research, we did not identify correlations between AI-related – GIS and AI-related – Decision Support (it emerged only in 2012 and has disappeared until now). AI-Related algorithms are already part of GIS systems but are “hidden” for our research since the authors did not mention them as keywords. Similarly, the lack of correlation between Decision Support and AI-Related suggested that either AI-Related is not used (unlikely) or is already embedded in the related software and, therefore, not identified by the authors (“hidden”). Considering already existing ML and DL algorithms embedded in other technologies, we could assume that the number of AI-Related papers would grow significantly, contributing to the hypothesis of its relevance and revolutionary character.

Cantrell and Holzman (2016) highlighted that implementing ML requires well-formed questions. At the same time, the learning performance of ML/DL should be measured and evaluated, which might go beyond landscape planners’ scope of expertise if realized in a programming environment. The speed and extent of the technological revolution we experience might cause the “technology lag,” the concept introduced by Susskind in 1996 (Susskind & Susskind, 2015). It stated that the ability of computer technology to capture, retrieve, and reproduce data exceeds the human ability to use the technology. It is a delay between data processing and knowledge processing. Bhartiya et al. (2022) emphasized that technology

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become more user-friendly and easy to use; nevertheless, there is a need for better understanding and constant observation since the field is evolving at a never-seen-before pace. According to Daniel and Pettit (2021), planners might be unaware of the solutions and tools available, be concerned about the costs and quality of the outcome, and experience overall uncertainty in adopting new technologies. Campagna (2016) claimed that innovation in a current LP practice could be critical to supporting the effective link between knowledge-building during research, synthesis, ideation, and decision-making. Giler-Velásquez et al. (2021) stressed the importance of mixed methods approaches, while von Richthofen et al. (2022) proposed a new framework to encompass the current technological advances. Our bibliographic analysis of journals found that the publications that targeted LP were in the minority. Most of them targeted at one side computer science and specific technology development, on the other: earth and environmental sciences (research-oriented technology application). It might contribute to the dichotomy between technology innovations and their actual planning applications and, as suggested by Geertman et al. (2020) and von Richthofen et al. (2022), calls for closer cooperation between LP practitioners, researchers, and IT specialists.

5. Conclusions

Q1 Which digital technologies are used in landscape planning?

We identified 35 technologies and grouped them into 12 main groups: Remote Sensing, GIS, Other Digital Modelling, AI-related, Other ICT, 3D Modelling, Data, Decision Support, Robotic, VR/AR/MR, Social Media, and CAD.

With their respective subgroups, they create a complex network of tools, software, and devices that can support the landscape planning process.

Q2 What are the emerging trends, and how have they changed over the last ten years?

The overall trend is a dynamic growth of the literature on the subject. We anticipate the AI-Related group to become a game changer due to the fastest growth in the number of papers tackling its application. On the other hand, some technologies like GIS might now become standard tools for LP. Therefore, they are not highlighted in the keywords, titles, and abstracts unless the publications focus on the innovation and research in the technology itself.

Q3 What are the dominant correlations between different digital technologies?

The dominant reciprocal correlations are between the Remote Sensing, Data (Big Data), and AI-Related (Machine Learning). The most significant correlation pairs are Remote Sensing and 3D Modelling, AI-Related and VR/AR/MR, GIS and Decision Support Systems, 3D Modelling and VR/AR/MR, Robotic and Remote Sensing. There was no correlation between Remote Sensing and GIS. GIS correlated with the Decision Support System (particularly with MCDA).

Q3 Where are the gaps for further research?

More knowledge of technologies explicitly targeting the LP is needed, including understanding and associating their feasibility and application for different process phases. Most of the technologies focus on the research phase of the planning process; the synthesis and ideation phases need more comprehensive development.

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The scoping literature review provided comprehensive information on technologies available for the landscape planning process. The next step is understanding their application and monitoring their advances to minimize the technology lag. It also calls for closer collaboration between IT specialists developing new tools and landscape planners and might require new frameworks for the whole process.

Systematic reviews should be conducted to understand the role of each technology group in the planning process. The hidden correlations between technologies should be thoroughly mapped to understand the complex technological system and gain the knowledge to use it effectively. New frameworks and mixed methods should be developed, including open-access toolboxes.

The reviewed database of the literature identified numerous further directions for the research:

- Assessing existing applications of digital technologies in the landscape planning education process and developing recommendations for future curriculum development,
- Analyzing the role of particular technologies in the planning process, such as VR, which have not been reviewed yet,
- Understanding and mapping the complexity of systems, overlaps, and intersections between technologies for landscape planning.

4.2 Study limitations

The review is based on the declarations of the authors of the publications. It means the classification quality strongly depends on the authors' approach, the publications' scope, and the level of detail provided in keywords, abstracts, and titles.

We were working manually on a limited set. New emerging technologies could be hidden from the automated data charting algorithms if they were not included in the training sets; even if they were reported, the algorithms did not detect them. Therefore, the algorithms should be trained with additional relevant keywords for each new data set, and manual verification should be applied.

Some of the technologies, such as GIS, are no longer reported by authors since they became standard practice in landscape planning. On the other hand, some technologies have become integral parts of other technologies, i.e., ML packages offered by GIS software or algorithms developed for Remote Sensing data extraction not identified by authors as AI-Related. Therefore, the relationships between technologies might go beyond the correlations identified in our research.

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